

CONDENSATION OF CHALKONES WITH FLAVANONES.

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A number of chalcones and flavanones have been condensed in presence of alkali or pulverised sodium, the latter being particularly effective.

The reactivity of the keto-ethylene group $\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{C}=\text{O}$ in chalcones has been the subject of a large number of investigations. Apart from the various reactions they undergo, they give rise to various addition reactions with compounds containing the reactive methylene group (Knoevenagel, *Annalen*, 1894, 281, 25; Hill, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1115). Consequently condensation of chalcones with compounds containing the keto-methylene in an open-chain such as acetoacetic ester and desoxybenzoin or in a homocyclic ring like *cyclohexanone* has been extensively studied. No work has, however, been done with compounds having the keto-methylene group in a heterocyclic ring. A study has now been made of the condensation of chalcones with flavanones. The latter contain the $\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2$ group as a part of a ring and it is of interest to see if inclusion in a heterocyclic ring affects the activity of the keto-methylene group. Inclusion in a carbonylic ring as in *cyclohexanone* does not inhibit the addition, and it has now been observed that the flavanones also add on normally as follows.—

where R is an aryl radical.

For the present investigation the following condensations were studied.

Chalcone.	Flavanone.	Condensing reagent.
(1) Phenylstyryl ketone	"	Sodium hydroxide
(2) <i>p</i> -Tolylstyryl ketone	"	"
(3) Phenyl-4'-methoxystyryl ketone	"	Sodium ethoxide
(4) <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -methoxystyryl ketone	"	Sodium in ether
(5) Phenyl-4'-methylstyryl ketone	"	"
(6) 4-Methylphenyl-4-methylstyryl ketone.	"	"
(7) Phenylstyryl ketone	(3':4')-Methylene-dioxyflavanone	"

(1) and (2) were successfully condensed by means of aqueous alcoholic sodium hydroxide but in the case of (3) the desired condensation was brought about by employing sodium ethoxide, due to the failure of sodium hydroxide. 4, 5, 6 and 7, however, could not be condensed by means of either of them and therefore resort was made to pulverised sodium in dry ether, which in our opinion is the best condensing agent for such reactions. These compounds were characterised by the formation of their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

Flavanone, however, could not be condensed with the following chalcones.

- (1) Phenyl-(3':4') methylenedioxy styryl ketone
- (2) *p*-Tolyl-(3':4') methylenedioxy styryl ketone
- (3) *o*-Hydroxyphenyl-(3':4') methylenedioxy styryl ketone
- (4) *o*-Methoxyphenyl-(3':4') methylenedioxy styryl ketone
- (5) 2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-nitrophenyl styryl ketone
- (6) 2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-nitrophenyl-4'-methoxystyryl ketone
- (7) 2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-nitrophenyl-4'-methylstyryl ketone

Thus some chalcones condense readily while others have so far resisted condensation. Although no definite generalisation can be drawn regarding the influence of substituents in the chalcone molecule, it appears that the presence of the (3':4') methylenedioxy group in chalcones retards condensations. The failure of the nitrochalcones to condense may be attributed to the deactivating effect of the nitro group, as had been observed before in similar types of reactions (*cf.* Hutchins, Motwani, Mudphatkal and Wheeler, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1882).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The compounds have been numbered for brevity. They were recrystallised from alcohol unless some other solvent is specified. They are all colourless unless otherwise mentioned.

Chalcones.—The following chalcones were prepared from the acetophenone and aldehyde components in presence of alcoholic alkali. (1) Phenylstyryl ketone (Kostanecki and Rosbach *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 1492). (2) *p*-Tolylstyryl ketone (Kostanecki and Rosbach, *loc. cit.*). (3) Phenyl-4'-methoxystyryl ketone (Kohler and Conant, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 1702). (4) 4-Methylphenyl-4'-methoxystyryl ketone (Petrow, *Ber.*, 1930, 63B, 901). (5) Phenyl-4'-methoxystyryl ketone (Hanzlick and Bianchi, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 2283). (6) 4-Methylphenyl-4'-methylstyryl ketone

(Stobbe and Bremer, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1929, 123, 1). All the chalkones are yellow.

Flavanones.—(7) Flavanone (Ryan and Cruess-Callaghan, *Proc. Roy. Irish Acad.*, 1929, 39, 126). (8) (3':4')-Methylenedioxyflavanone (Ryan and Cruess-Callaghan. *loc. cit.*). (9) 3-(*o*-Phenyl- β -benzoyl-ethyl) flavanone. (9) was obtained in the following manner. To an alcoholic solution of 10 g. each of (1) and (7), 2.5 g. of 25% sodium hydroxide solution were added. The mixture was vigorously stirred and allowed to stand in the frigidaire overnight. The solid which settled at the bottom was carefully washed with dilute hydrochloric acid in order to remove away the sodium salt, if any, and filtered, m.p. 149-51°, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 83.2; H, 5.6. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 83.3; H, 5.6 per cent).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of (9) was obtained by heating under reflux an alcoholic solution of (9) and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine. Recrystallised from alcohol-acetone it separated in orange coloured needles m.p. 229-30°. (Found: N, 9.0. $C_{20}H_{12}O_6N_4$ requires N, 9.2 per cent). In the similar manner 3-[*o*-phenyl- β -(*p*)-toluoyl-ethyl] flavanone (10) was isolated from (2) and (7). (Found: C, 83.3; H, 5.8. $C_{21}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 83.4; H, 5.8 per cent). In exactly the same way as before its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was obtained. Recrystallised from acetic acid it was obtained as yellowish red needles, m.p. 237-39°. (Found: N, 9.0. $C_{27}H_{20}O_6N_4$ requires N, 8.9 per cent).

3-(*o*-Anisyl- β -benzoyl-ethyl) flavanone (11) was produced by allowing an alcoholic solution of (3) and (7) to stand overnight in presence of sodium ethoxide, m.p. 92-94°. (Found: C, 79.2; H, 5.4. $C_{21}H_{18}O_4$, $\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires C, 79.0; H, 5.7 per cent).

3-(*o*-Anisyl- β -*p*-toluoyl-ethyl) flavanone (12) was obtained by refluxing for 5 hours ethereal solution of (4) and (7) in presence of a suspension of pulverised sodium. The paste so formed solidified on boiling with alcohol, m.p. 90-92°. (Found: C, 80.6; H, 5.4. $C_{22}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 80.7; H, 5.9 per cent).

In exactly the same manner as (12), 3-(*o*-*p*-tolyl- β -benzoyl-ethyl)-flavanone (13) (Found: C, 82.1; H, 6.0. $C_{21}H_{18}O_2$, $\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires C, 81.8; H, 6.0 per cent) and 3-(*o*-*p*-tolyl- β -toluoyl-ethyl) flavanone (14) (Found: C, 80.5; H, 6.2. $C_{22}H_{20}O_2$, H_2O requires C, 80.3, H, 6.3 per cent) were obtained by condensing (5) and (6) with (7) respectively.

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of (13) of orange colour, m.p. 252-55° (Found: N, 9.2. $C_{27}H_{20}O_6N_4$ requires N, 8.9 per cent) was obtained as

usual. Similarly 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of (14) of orange colour, m. p. 249-51° was isolated. (Found: N, 8.4. $C_{28}H_{22}O_6N_4$ requires N, 8.8 per cent.) (3':4')-Methylenedioxy-3-(α -phenyl- β -benzoylethyl) flavanone (15) was obtained as stated above, by using pulverised sodium as a condensing agent. Recrystallised from acetic acid it melted at 184-85°. (Found: C, 77.7; H, 5.2. $C_{31}H_{24}O_8$ requires C, 78.1; H, 5.0 per cent). 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of (15) was obtained as usual by refluxing an alcoholic solution of (15) and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine. Recrystallised from acetic acid it was obtained as orange-red needles and melted at 228°-30°. (Found: N, 8.2. $C_{37}H_{28}O_8N_4$ requires N, 8.5 per cent.)

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Received December 27, 1941.
